

Experimentally, How Does Cu TSV Diameter Influence its Stress State?

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I. ABSTRACT

In this work, an experimental study of the influence of Cu through-silicon via (TSV) diameter on stress build up was performed using synchrotron-based X-ray microdiffraction technique. Three Cu TSV diameters were studied; 3 μm , 5 μm and 8 μm , all of which were fabricated in a single chip. Prior to the measurements, the die was annealed at 420 °C (30 min), yielding a fully grown and stable microstructure. The measured mean hydrostatic stresses in the Cu TSV were 185±14 MPa (3 μm Cu TSV diameter), 147±10 MPa (5 μm Cu TSV diameter) and 205±15 MPa (8 μm Cu TSV diameter). As such, no conclusive stress dependence on Cu TSV diameter was determined. This is attributed to stress relaxation mechanisms including plastic deformation, grain boundary sliding, dislocation motion and the formation of cracks/ voids which are otherwise neglected in many reported finite element modeling based studies. Additionally, this study underscores that the stress-strain behavior of Cu TSVs are significantly dependent on their thermal history and microstructural characteristics.

II. INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional integrated circuits (3D-IC) are made possible by the use of vertical interconnects called through-silicon via (TSV). TSVs enables the achievement of the shortest interconnects between stacked chips as well as allowing for high density input/outputs, thereby resulting in high performance of 3D-IC chips. Due to the better electrical conductivity and electro-migration resistance, copper has become the preferred filling material for TSVs [1]. In order to attain a sustained improvement in the performance of the 3D-IC chips, the TSV interconnect density should consistently increase. This can be achieved by the reduction of the TSV diameter, allowing for increased interconnect density. However, due to the mismatch in the material properties of Cu TSV and the surrounding Si matrix, stresses are generated in and around the Cu TSVs, which is a major reliability concern [2]. As such, changing the diameter of Cu TSVs from its current diameter of about 8 μm – 5 μm , to a smaller dimension, requires that a full analysis of the potential reliability consequence be established [3].

The potential thermo-mechanical consequences of changing the Cu TSV diameter, has necessitated many studies. However, most of the reported work is based on finite element analysis (FEA) studies [4],[5],[6]. Only two experimental studies based on synchrotron microdiffraction

technique have been reported in this domain [7], [8]. The work of [7] is an indirect assessment of the impact of Cu TSV diameter, as only the stresses in Si were determined and not the stresses in the Cu TSVs themselves. The measurements were performed at 150 °C and the samples only witnessed a thermal treatment of 150 °C (1 hr), prior to their measurement. As such, their grain structure is still unstable, as further annealing treatment will lead to a change in their microstructural characteristics. On the other hand, [8] measured the stresses in Cu TSVs for two different diameters. However, the two Cu TSV diameters were fabricated by two different manufacturers; with different thermal histories, electrodeposition chemistries and aspect ratios. Due to these numerous differences, it is difficult to draw any scientifically meaningful and quantitative conclusions from the result from that study.

In this work, we present a systematic study aimed at addressing the deficiencies of the reported works. The stress in otherwise identical TSVs with different diameters was experimentally determined using the synchrotron-based X-ray microdiffraction technique. The measured Cu TSVs were all in a single chip; having the same processing conditions, electrodeposition chemistry and depth. To ensure a fully grown and stable Cu TSV microstructure, the sample was annealed at 420 °C (30 min), before measurements were performed at room temperature.

III. EXPERIMENT

In this study, a SEMATCH [9] fabricated chip with blind Cu TSVs arrays of different diameters was used for this experiment (see Fig. 1). The Cu TSVs studied were 3 μm , 5 μm and 8 μm in diameter, while all the measured Cu TSVs have the same depth of 50 μm .

The test sample was coated with 410 nm of plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposited SiO₂ (PECVD). Afterwards it was annealed at 420 °C for 30 min. Synchrotron-based X-ray microdiffraction studies were used to measure the stresses and strains in the Cu TSVs. While the atomic force microscopy (AFM) technique was used as a complimentary tool for measuring the topography of the Cu TSVs.

The X-ray microdiffraction measurements were performed at sector 34-ID-E, of the Advanced Photon Source (APS), Argonne National Laboratory. The experimental procedure used is similar to those previously reported in [10],[11],[12],[13],[14]. The procedure includes the use of

both polychromatic and monochromatic X-rays, three area detectors and a depth profiler. Measurements were performed along the entire length of the 50 μm Cu TSVs at an interval of 5 μm .

Fig. 1: Optical image of the test chip used for this study, which contains Cu TSV arrays of different diameters and pitches. Insert (a) 3 μm diameter Cu TSV (b) 5 μm diameter Cu TSV (c) 8 μm diameter Cu TSV

Fig. 2: AFM topograph image of nine Cu TSVs with 3 μm diameter.

Tapping mode AFM measurements were performed to characterize the topography of the protruding Cu TSV with respect to their diameter.

All error bars reported in this study is one standard deviation. For the stress measurement data, the error bars are due to the uncertainties associated with the diffracted X-ray peak positions on the area detectors and uncertainties in the lattice spacing determination. For the AFM measurements, the error bars are due to Cu TSV- to - Cu TSV topography variability.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 3 – 5, present the results of the normal stresses in the 3 μm , 5 μm and 8 μm Cu TSV diameters, respectively. For the 3 μm diameter Cu TSV, shown in Fig. 3, the stresses with respect to depth is measured to be approximately between 150 MPa and 250 MPa, with the exception of the central region (27.5 μm depth). At the central region, a minimum stress of about 50 MPa is observed. This dramatic dip in the stress is attributed to the possible presence of voids/cracks at the center of the TSV, which acts as a stress relief sink.

Fig. 3: Depth dependent measurement of the normal stresses and the hydrostatic stresses in the 3 μm diameter Cu TSV.

Fig. 4: Depth dependent measurement of the normal stresses and the hydrostatic stresses in the 5 μm diameter Cu TSV.

Fig. 5: Depth dependent measurement of the normal stresses and the hydrostatic stresses in the 8 μm diameter Cu TSV.

Fig. 6: Mean hydrostatic stresses in the different Cu TSV diameters.

For the 5 μm diameter Cu TSV, presented in Fig. 4, the stresses across its entire length are more uniformly distributed than that of the 3 μm diameter Cu TSV (Fig. 3). As the maximum dip in stresses (being the difference between the maximum and the minimum stress values) for the 3 μm and 5 μm diameter Cu TSVs are about 210 MPa and 80 MPa, respectively. This is attributed to the minimal presence of possible voids/cracks in the 5 μm diameter Cu TSV. On the other hand, the measured stresses in the 5 μm diameter Cu TSVs are generally lower than that witnessed in the 3 μm diameter Cu TSV, as its stresses varied between ≈ 120 MPa and ≈ 200 MPa.

For the 8 μm diameter Cu TSV (Fig. 5), a maximum stress of ≈ 300 MPa is measured at the 32.5 μm depth, while the minimum stresses were observed at the ends of the Cu TSV. In comparison to the 3 μm and 5 μm Cu TSV diameters, the stresses in the 8 μm diameter Cu TSV are much higher.

To ease the comparison of the stresses in the different Cu TSV diameters, their mean hydrostatic stresses were calculated and are presented in Fig. 6. The mean hydrostatic stresses were obtained by averaging the hydrostatic stresses along the entire length of the Cu TSVs.

From Fig. 6, it can be clearly seen that the minimum and the maximum stresses occurred in the 5 μm and the 8 μm diameter Cu TSVs, respectively. Their mean hydrostatic stresses were 185±14 MPa (3 μm Cu TSV diameter), 147±10 MPa (5 μm Cu TSV diameter) and 205±15 MPa (8 μm Cu TSV diameter). Thus, no clear correlation was determined between the built up stresses and the diameter of the Cu TSVs, as the observed stresses did not increase monotonically with increasing TSV diameter. This result contradicts many published FEM based studies which predict that Cu TSV stresses will increase with increasing TSV diameter [4], [5], [6] and the experimental studies performed by [7].

The reason for this unclear relationship between stress and Cu TSV diameter may be deduced from the AFM topography measurements presented in Fig. 7 – 8. Fig. 7 shows that Cu is protruding from the TSVs; the maximum vertical Cu protrusion increased monotonically with increasing Cu TSV diameter (Fig. 8). Additionally, the protruded Cu is observed to be mushroom-like in shape, in that the width of the protruding Cu is larger than the diameter of the Cu TSVs. For instance, the width of the protrusion for the 3 μm, 5 μm and 8 μm diameter Cu TSVs are 4.5 μm, 8 μm and 12 μm respectively.

Fig. 7: AFM profile of the protruding Cu for the different Cu TSV diameters.

The observation of Cu protrusion signifies that the Cu TSVs have yielded plastically, indicating that the elastic limit has been exceeded for all Cu TSV diameters. As such,

the Cu TSVs no longer could accommodate more stresses, as the peak stress threshold has been reached. This suggests that the stresses in the Cu TSVs are not anticipated to monotonically increase with TSV diameter, as has been predicted by the FEM based studies [4],[5],[6].

Fig. 8: Statistical representation of the maximum vertical protrusion of the Cu TSVs with respect to diameter.

Additionally, Cu protrusion (Fig. 7 and 8) is aided by grain boundary sliding (GBS) [15]. GBS mechanism involves the translation of one grain over another, parallel to the boundary interface [16]. GBS results in the formation of voids and cracks, which enables the relaxation of stresses in the Cu TSV [17]. As such, GBS is anticipated to contribute significantly to the unclear relationship between stress buildup and the diameter of Cu TSV.

Also, rate-controlled dislocation motion is known to aid stress relaxation even in the absence of voids/cracks [18]. This is found to be true for Cu TSVs also, as we have reported in [13]. The amount of stress relaxation achieved through dislocation motion will be dependent on the characteristics of the microstructure of the polycrystalline Cu, as such, may not scale with the diameter of the Cu TSVs [19].

The discrepancy in the results presented in this work, is related to the used annealing temperature. In this study the samples were annealed at 420 °C (30 min) after SiO₂ deposition at 300 °C, while for the studies reported in [7], a maximum annealing treatment post Cu filling was at 150 °C (1 hr). This infers that microstructure of the two studies are very different, as full grown and stable microstructure is expected in this study [20], [21], [22] as opposed to a meta-stable microstructural state [6] in the study done by [7]. This is because additional annealing treatments such as the deposition of the back-end-of-line dielectrics often done in the upwards of 300 °C, will result in grain growth in [7], while no such changes in expected in this study as 420 °C is the maximum temperature that the dies will ever witness throughout its lifetime.

The low annealing temperature of 150 °C means that limited plastic deformation, void formation/growth is expected in [7], as compared to that in this study, leading to lower relaxation of stresses. Additionally, since GBS is occurs $\geq 0.4T_m$ (which is 433 °C for pure Cu), this means that GBS mechanism is not operating actively in the Cu TSVs studied in [7], thereby limiting stress relaxation in the Cu TSVs. As such the Cu TSVs studied in [7] behave more elastically, leading to the scaling of Si stresses with the diameter of the Cu TSVs as their results showed.

Therefore, the differences in our studies and that done by [7], shows clearly that the stresses in Cu TSVs are significantly dependent on the thermal history and microstructure of the Cu TSVs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we experimentally evaluated the effect of Cu TSV diameter on stress buildup. Depth dependent measurements of the stresses were determined using the synchrotron-based X-ray microdiffraction method, while the AFM technique was used to study the protrusion of Cu.

From this study it is found that the stresses in the Cu TSV did not scale with its diameter, as the measured mean hydrostatic stresses were 185±14 MPa (3 μm Cu TSV diameter), 147±10 MPa (5 μm Cu TSV diameter) and 205±15 MPa (8 μm Cu TSV diameter).

From the AFM topography measurements, the reason for this unclear trend between stress and Cu TSV diameter were determined. The AFM measurements clearly show that the Cu TSVs, irrespective of their diameter yielded plastically. Plastic deformation observation is a clear evidence that the elastic limit of the Cu has been exceeded. This means that the stresses in the Cu TSV are not expected to necessarily scale with TSV diameter.

Additionally, the observation of Cu protrusion is an evidence of the operation of the GBS mechanism. This results in the formation of cracks and voids which allows for the relaxation of the stresses in the Cu TSV.

Also, rate-controlled dislocation motion is anticipated to influence the stress state of Cu TSVs, by initiating stress relaxation. The magnitude of the achieved stress relaxation will be mainly dependent on the microstructure of the Cu TSVs rather than on their diameter.

This means that the factors that govern the stress state of Cu TSVs are complex and non-linear, contrary to that reported in FEA-based studies. As such, this work underscores the need for more robust simulation methodologies that takes into account the polycrystalline nature of Cu TSVs and their complex deformation and stress relaxation mechanisms.

Additionally, the thermal history as well as the microstructure of the Cu TSVs has a strong impact on the stress state of the Cu TSVs.

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VII. REFERENCES

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